

DEVELOPMENT AND STRENGTHENING OF STUDENTS' CORRECT READING SKILLS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

Reading is a multifaceted skill that can permeate all aspects of life. Having strong reading skills allows us to interpret and find meaning in everything we read, and as we continue to improve these skills, we also develop our ability to communicate effectively through writing. This article discusses the development and strengthening of students' reading skills in English classes.

Keywords: reading skills, reading comprehension, communication skills, English classes.

Аннотация

Чтение — это многогранный навык, который может проникнуть во все аспекты жизни. Наличие сильных навыков чтения позволяет нам интерпретировать и находить смысл во всем, что мы читаем, и по мере того, как мы продолжаем улучшать эти навыки, мы также развиваем нашу способность эффективно общаться посредством письма. В данной статье рассматривается развитие и укрепление навыков чтения учащихся на уроках английского языка.

Ключевые слова: навыки чтения, понимание прочитанного, коммуникативные навыки, занятия английским языком.

Reading skills are skills that relate to a person's ability to read, understand, interpret, and decode written language and texts. Exceptional reading skills can be very useful for understanding and responding to written messages such as emails, messages, letters, and other written messages. Using reading skills in the workplace can also be important to ensure effective written communication, which can lead to fewer miscommunications or misunderstandings of expectations. Reading skills can include several key aspects that work together to develop general literacy skills, including comprehension, fluency, vocabulary, and strategies that help students interpret and find meaning in texts.

Reading comprehension is simply the ability to understand what you read. Strong reading comprehension typically involves a variety of literacy skills needed to interpret and identify meanings within a text. Several elements, such as fluency, the ability to decode unfamiliar vocabulary, and the use of contextual clues from reading to identify key features of a text, may be components of effective reading comprehension.

Fluency refers to a combination of various factors. First, it focuses on the ability to read clearly with the flow. Fluency also focuses on the ability to quickly decode new vocabulary while reading. Fluency is something like reading, it can directly affect our ability to understand what we read. For example, when a child becomes fluent in reading, he can quickly find the meaning and understanding of what he reads, which contributes to understanding the text.

The ability to decode or determine the meaning of new words can also affect reading comprehension. If new meanings are quickly interpreted and relationships between new vocabulary and familiar terms are identified, the student can improve their ability to make inferences, form ideas, and generally gain a better understanding of the texts they read.

Inferencing is also a key element of reading comprehension. When we infer, we connect information from texts to our own ideas and thoughts to help us make sense of what we read. For example, when reading an article about plastics in the oceans, we might conclude that we need to recycle to reduce the amount of plastic waste. Inference happens when we read a text where the purpose and meaning of the text is not clearly stated. In addition, the ability to connect ideas and draw conclusions helps to increase recall.

Reading comprehension is usually about retaining what we read. Understanding is based on the retention of information. By practicing inference skills and remembering what we read, we can further strengthen our reading comprehension.

There are many ways to improve your reading skills. Whenever we come across unfamiliar vocabulary, we can practice speed reading or make notes to improve our fluency. The following steps will also help us identify what we can do to improve and further develop our study skills.

One of the most effective ways to improve our skills is to practice. Developing our reading skills ultimately takes practice, and we can set aside 10-15 minutes to study

each day. If we take the time to practice our reading skills, we can read news articles, fiction, magazine issues, or any text.

We can set reading goals for ourselves that help us develop a wider vocabulary, deepen our understanding of different texts, and improve our ability to make connections between what we read and our own perspectives and ideas.

Previewing and scanning texts can be another step towards improving your reading skills. We can use this strategy by previewing headings, subheadings, and other text features to get an idea of what we are reading about. This helps to form the main ideas about the text before starting to read it.

When reading different texts, it is necessary to practice determining the purpose. Think about why different texts were written and what meanings or themes can be understood from the text. We can also identify the purpose of what we are reading, such as finding information, following instructions in a manual, or enjoying a story. Knowing our purpose in reading a text helps us look for main ideas and details that support our purpose.

When we read a variety of texts, we can use several key strategies to help us increase our understanding. For example, when previewing a text, we can identify the structure of the text as informative, persuasive, or instructional. We can also identify key elements of different texts, such as central themes, problems and solutions, or comparative ideas presented as we read. Using strategies such as identifying text features, targeting, and note taking can help us improve our reading skills.

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